

Synthesis and Characterization of CeO₂ Nanoparticles through Precipitation

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ABSTRACT

Cerium oxide nanoparticles (CeO₂) have been synthesized through precipitation in aqueous medium at room temperature using cerium III nitrate hexahydrate (Ce(NO₃)₃·6H₂O) as precursor and poly(vinylpyrrolidinone) (PVP) as surfactant. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) was used to evaluate cluster formation and Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images were obtained in order to determine the shape, average size and uniformity of the nanoparticles. The elements presented (cerium and oxygen) in the nanoparticles were confirmed through energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS). X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns indicated the formation of cerium oxide with cubic structure and lattice parameters of 5.41036 Å. Average crystallite size was found to be 5.47 nm and no other crystalline phase was detected.

Keywords: Cerium oxide, nanoparticles, precipitation, X-ray diffraction.

INTRODUCTION

The synthesis and utilization of nanoparticles have been largely studied due to their unique characteristics compared to their corresponding bulk materials. To be considered nanoparticles, crystals or clusters with at least one of their dimensions less than 100 nm must form the synthesized powder. As the material reaches nanoscale, the percentage of atoms at the crystal surface becomes significant enough to have an effect on its physical and chemical properties [1]. Superior diffusivity, higher mechanical strength, greater chemical reactivity and lower electrical resistivity are examples of nanoparticle features that have been reported [2].

In this sense, cerium oxide (CeO₂) nanoparticles, also known as nanoceria, have been used to improve several processes, such as their application as catalytic converters in automotive systems [3]. In addition, nanoceria has been reported to be an effective oxygen sensor in absorption analysis [4]. Regarding biological features, CeO₂ nanoparticles have shown antioxidant activity similar to the enzyme superoxide dismutase, besides their capacity to protect neural and ocular cells [5]. The versatility of this nanomaterial is a result of oxygen defects in the crystalline structure from reduction of Ce⁴⁺ to Ce³⁺ ions in its surface. These reactive spots are capable of capturing free reactive oxygen species (ROS), such as hydroxyl radical, peroxides, and superoxide. In inflammatory reactions, ROS are highly formed, which appoints ceria nanoparticles as potential anti-inflammatory agents [6].

The most common synthesizing methods to produce CeO₂ nanoparticles can be divided into two categories: low temperature processes, usually below 250 °C; and high temperature routes, reaching over 1000 °C and including combustion or plasma formation. High temperature synthesis demands greater energetic cost and operational complexity. Alkoxide or carboxylate aerosols are typically the precursor in these processes, being continuously fed into reaction chambers. Other high temperature techniques can be cited, such as physical vapor synthesis and calcination. Usually, nanoparticles produce at temperatures over 1000 °C have shown greater sizes, prismatic shape and higher propensity to form agglomerates than the ones synthesized at mild conditions [4].

Low temperature syntheses normally include chemical reactions in

aqueous medium. Precipitation, sol-gel, hydrothermal, and micro emulsion methods are among the most employed routes. This group of techniques is more accessible to small scale and laboratorial research, because of its simplicity and low operational cost. Usually, a reactant with Ce³⁺ is oxidized into Ce⁴⁺, a less soluble ion. The precipitation of CeO₂ occurs once the thermodynamic stable concentration in a supersaturated solution is exceeded [4]. Organic stabilizers can be used to prevent re-nucleation, in order to obtain particles with great uniformity and smaller sizes [7]. Yu *et al.* (2000) has presented the production of ceria nanoparticles through this method using sodium hydroxide as oxidant under stirring. Sodium nitrate was a by-product of this route, as shown in the following equation:

According to the authors, NaNO₃ has been found to be highly soluble, which permitted that Na⁺ and NO₃⁻ ions to surround the recently produced ceria nanoparticles. That ensured smaller particles and diminished agglomeration [5].

In this study, the synthesis of CeO₂ nanoparticles through precipitation at room temperature is presented. The produced ceria NP's were characterized through SEM, TEM, XDR and EDS in order to evaluate their composition, size, and crystalline structure.

METHODOLOGY

Commercial cerium III nitrate hexahydrate (Ce(NO₃)₃·6H₂O, Neon Comercial®, Brazil) was dissolved in DI water to produce a 21 wt.%. The mass of one gram of poly(vinylpyrrolidinone) (PVP, Sigma-Aldrich®) was added as the stabilizer to a sodium hydroxide (NaOH, Dinâmica Ltd., Brazil) 4 wt.% solution under stirring [8]. Ce(NO₃)₃·6H₂O solution was then added to the system dropwise and the resulting solution was kept under vigorous stirring for one hour. The precipitate was filtered and washed several times with a 1:1 ration solution of ethanol (C₂H₆O, Dinâmica Ltd., Brazil) and DI water. The material was dried at

110 °C for 24 hours and sintered at 600 °C for 2 hours. All chemicals were used without further purification.

CeO₂ nanoparticles were characterized for morphological and sizing determination by scanning electron microscope (SEM, JSM-6610LV) and a transmission electron microscope (TEM, Jeol JEM-1400). The powder was also analyzed through energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS, Shimadzu SEM-EDS) to confirm the chemical composition of ceria nanoparticles. X-ray powder diffraction (XRD, Rigaku SmartLab) was operated at 30 mA with CuK α radiation and 40 KeV for phase identification and crystalline sizing.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

TEM micrographs of synthesized CeO₂ nanoparticles are shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. TEM micrographs of CeO₂ nanoparticles.

The spherical format observed by TEM was similar to other reports on CeO₂ nanoparticles [5] By using the *ImageJ*[®] software, the diameters of both particles on Fig. 1(a) were found to be 8 nm and 14 nm. The size distribution estimation of Fig. 1(b) carried out through the same software shown that 64% of ceria nanoparticles have measured to be between 4.5 to 6.5 nm in diameter, as shown in Table 1. The average size was 6.86 nm with 2.69 nm standard deviation.

Table 1. Size distribution of CeO₂ nanoparticles by TEM analysis.

Group	Size (nm)	Percentage (%)
1	4.5 - 6.5	64.86
2	6.5 - 8.5	16.22
3	8.5 - 10.5	13.51
4	12.5 <	5.41
		100

Hence, the powder nanoscale dimensions was confirmed, which indicates that the synthesis method succeed to produce ceria nanoparticles. Based on TEM micrographs, the nanoparticles have shown satisfying uniformity regarding their format. As for size uniformity, the diameter values fairly deviated from the average, which could be improved by the addition of other organic stabilizers [2]. In addition, Zhang *et al.* (2004) have reported that reaction times around 85 minutes produced more uniform nanoparticles with less size variations [9].

The structural parameters and phase purity have been investigated by X-ray diffraction based on the International Center for Diffraction Data (ICDD). The XDR patterns of CeO₂

nanoparticles are shown in Fig. (2).

Figure 2. X-ray diffraction pattern of CeO₂ nanoparticles.

The pattern analysis using Match 3.4 software has revealed the nanoparticles composition as CeO₂ and their structure to be cubic (space group Fm-3m and JCPDS no. 34-394). Lattice parameters were determined as $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$ and $a = b = c = 5.41036 \text{ \AA}$, similarly to the literature reported value of 5.41134 \AA [10]. The crystallite size was found to be 5.47 nm, a value in the range between 4.5 e 6.5 nm observed by TEM. No secondary phase was detected from the XRD analysis, indicating that the ceria nanoparticles had great purity.

SEM images of CeO₂ nanoparticles and PVP samples are presented in Fig. (3).

Figure 3. SEM images of CeO₂ nanoparticles (a) and a PVP (b) samples.

In Fig. 3(a), it can be seen CeO₂ clusters with sizes less than 10 μm . Similarly to the uniformity issue, aggregation could be diminished through changes in the synthesis route, such as longer reaction time and addition of more than one organic stabilizer [9]. The PVP clusters observed in Fig. 3(b) did not compromised the synthesis since this polymer has high solubility in water. Moreover, after sintering, no trace of PVP was observed on XRD patterns.

CeO₂ nanoparticles were examined by EDS, resulting in the spectrum showed in Fig. 4.

Figure 4. EDS spectrum for CeO₂ nanoparticles.

EDS results have confirmed the presence of cerium and oxygen

elements in the CeO₂ nanoparticles. The peak between 2.0 and 2.5 KeV was identified as background by the EDS equipment and did not indicate any element that could possibly contaminate the samples. It could be due to the EDS limitations, since this technique presents lower resolution in comparison to other X-ray analyses [11]. Table 2 shows a qualitative and semi-quantitative determination of nanoparticles composition by EDS. These results demonstrate that the synthesis method accomplished to produce ceria nanoparticles with high purity.

Table 2. Qualitative and semi-quantitative determination of CeO₂ nanoparticles composition by EDS.

Element	Percentage (wt.%)
Ce	67.403
O	32.597
Total	100.000

CONCLUSION

The presented study reported the synthesis and characterization of CeO₂ nanoparticles through precipitation. The process has been found to be able to produce nanoscale powder for several applications. TEM images revealed good format uniformity and decent size distribution, with most particles presenting dimensions between 4.5 and 6.5 nm. XRD analysis indicated the cubic structure of the powder, with crystallite size of 5.47 nm. SEM micrographs showed some level of aggregation and EDS data have not shown the presence of contaminants. In general, the results presented in this study demonstrate the synthesis of high pure

CeO₂ nanoparticles through a simple route, with great potential to be used in biomedical, electronic and optical studies.

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